

ISic3449

prayer of two brothers

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta

Coordinates

37.307741, 14.710805

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5195

Physical Description

A thick slab, with remains of a moulded cornice along the upper front edge

Dimensions

Height 56 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 28 cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek text, laid out with some care. A vertical line indicates the left margin.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 45 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation not measured: mm

Text

1. Εὐχή Πανχα [ρίου]
2. καὶ Ἰωάννο [υ]
3. ἀδελφοὶ ἀδελποὶ (vac. undefined)

Apparatus

Text after Rizzone 2009

Translation (en)

Prayer of Pancharios and Ioannos, brothers

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491432

EDCS 55702038

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2009.0440

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1108

Cordano, Federica 2005. Epigrafi. In Maniscalco, Laura(eds.), *Museo Civico "Corrado Tamburino Merlini" di Mineo: sezione archeologica.* Mineo. pp. 119-125. At 122

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica.* 71: 426-437. At 434-435 no.3 fig.5

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica.* Trento. pp. 105-111. At 108 no.7

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